

Supplementary Tables and figures

Table S1. Weibull parameters and different wind speed characteristics for year 2016-17.

Height (m)	Method	k	c (m/s)	V _{avg} (m/s)	PD (W/m ²)	ED (kWh/m ²)	V _{mp} (m/s)	V _{me} (m/s)
120	EML	2.7745	9.1803	8.1718	471.6778	4131.8977	7.8144	11.1641
	EMJ	2.7745	9.1803	8.1718	471.6748	4131.8715	7.8144	11.1641
	EPF	2.7448	9.1839	8.1718	474.8738	4159.8941	7.7865	11.2106
	MoM	2.7680	9.1811	8.1718	472.3732	4137.9892	7.8084	11.1743
	MMLM	2.7769	9.1573	8.1516	467.9328	4099.0915	7.7973	11.1328
	GM	2.4079	9.3350	8.2759	540.4993	4734.7737	7.4701	11.9996
100	EML	2.8410	8.7759	7.8189	407.2156	3567.2082	7.5330	10.5868
	EMJ	2.8410	8.7762	7.8192	407.2602	3567.5992	7.5333	10.5872
	EPF	2.7938	8.7819	7.8192	411.4419	3604.2308	7.4940	10.6542
	MoM	2.8350	8.7770	7.8192	407.7763	3572.1200	7.5285	10.5955
	MMLM	2.8516	8.7564	7.8027	403.7811	3537.1223	7.5259	10.5502
	GM	2.4992	8.9066	7.9024	457.6806	4009.2822	7.2595	11.2688
80	EML	2.8732	8.3316	7.4264	346.5793	3036.0350	7.1791	10.0136
	EMJ	2.8732	8.3321	7.4268	346.6361	3036.5320	7.1795	10.0141
	EPF	2.8068	8.3398	7.4268	351.5537	3079.6100	7.1285	10.1018
	MoM	2.8675	8.3328	7.4268	347.0417	3040.0850	7.1753	10.0214
	MMLM	2.8763	8.3163	7.4131	344.4921	3017.7500	7.1685	9.9916
	GM	2.6053	8.3941	7.4561	373.3297	3270.3680	6.9703	10.4456
60	EML	2.8468	7.8293	6.9760	288.8568	2530.3860	6.7252	9.4384
	EMJ	2.8468	7.8296	6.9763	288.8913	2530.6880	6.7254	9.4388
	EPF	2.7665	7.8381	6.9763	293.9996	2575.4370	6.6649	9.5414
	MoM	2.8409	7.8302	6.9763	289.2523	2533.8500	6.7212	9.4461
	MMLM	2.8298	7.8194	6.9656	288.6086	2528.2120	6.7028	9.4455
	GM	2.6777	7.8655	6.9927	302.3424	2648.5190	6.6053	9.6874
40	EML	2.7194	7.1181	6.3316	222.1976	1946.4510	6.0138	8.7178
	EMJ	2.7194	7.1178	6.3313	222.1739	1946.2440	6.0136	8.7175
	EPF	2.6379	7.1250	6.3313	226.6605	1985.5460	5.9474	8.8245
	MoM	2.7123	7.1185	6.3313	222.5454	1949.4980	6.0081	8.7264
	MMLM	2.6820	7.1148	6.3257	223.5748	1958.5150	5.9788	8.7576
	GM	2.6835	7.1391	6.3474	225.8035	1978.0380	6.0005	8.7857
20	EML	2.3976	6.0527	5.3655	147.7829	1294.5780	4.8327	7.7951
	EMJ	2.3976	6.0512	5.3642	147.6697	1293.5860	4.8315	7.7931
	EPF	2.3461	6.0533	5.3642	150.2098	1315.8380	4.7770	7.8727
	MoM	2.3880	6.0516	5.3642	148.1305	1297.6230	4.8216	7.8076
	MMLM	2.3777	6.0577	5.3692	149.0504	1305.6810	4.8154	7.8307
	GM	2.5105	6.0559	5.3737	143.4452	1256.5800	4.9464	7.6478

Table S2. Weibull parameters and different wind speed characteristics for year 2017-18.

Height (m)	Method	k	c (m/s)	V _{avg} (m/s)	PD (W/m ²)	ED (kWh/m ²)	V _{mp} (m/s)	V _{me} (m/s)
120	EML	2.7965	9.0927	8.0962	455.9060	3993.7365	7.7618	11.0276
	EMJ	2.7965	9.0928	8.0963	455.9208	3993.8664	7.7619	11.0277
	EPF	2.7357	9.1001	8.0963	462.2394	4049.2170	7.7058	11.1214
	MoM	2.7901	9.0935	8.0963	456.5628	3999.4903	7.7562	11.0373
	MMLM	2.7706	9.0708	8.0739	454.7677	3983.7649	7.7173	11.0363
	GM	2.5632	9.1745	8.1455	491.6724	4307.0502	7.5647	11.4897
100	EML	2.9245	8.6438	7.7103	383.4034	3358.6135	7.4914	10.3297
	EMJ	2.9245	8.6445	7.7109	383.4984	3359.4456	7.4920	10.3306
	EPF	2.8561	8.6529	7.7109	388.8634	3406.4432	7.4409	10.4201
	MoM	2.9193	8.6452	7.7109	383.8909	3362.8842	7.4883	10.3372
	MMLM	2.9577	8.6303	7.7020	379.7017	3326.1866	7.5065	10.2771
	GM	2.6601	8.7271	7.7570	414.0015	3626.6531	7.3096	10.7747
80	EML	3.0107	8.1562	7.2845	318.0655	2786.2539	7.1328	9.6598
	EMJ	3.0107	8.1572	7.2854	318.1870	2787.3181	7.1337	9.6610
	EPF	2.9140	8.1687	7.2854	324.1188	2839.2805	7.0714	9.7731
	MoM	3.0064	8.1578	7.2854	318.4408	2789.5412	7.1310	9.6658
	MMLM	3.0463	8.1438	7.2772	315.0810	2760.1098	7.1466	9.6113
	GM	2.7483	8.2054	7.3015	338.0481	2961.3010	6.9602	10.0117
60	EML	3.0246	7.6111	6.7990	257.9714	2259.8296	6.6652	9.0018
	EMJ	3.0246	7.6122	6.8000	258.0753	2260.7396	6.6661	9.0030
	EPF	2.9069	7.6252	6.8000	263.9224	2311.9602	6.5957	9.1299
	MoM	3.0204	7.6126	6.8000	258.2723	2262.4658	6.6637	9.0073
	MMLM	3.0298	7.6009	6.7904	256.7454	2249.0901	6.6596	8.9850
	GM	2.8078	7.6518	6.8143	271.1582	2375.3459	6.5413	9.2674
40	EML	2.9170	6.8524	6.1117	191.2397	1675.2593	5.9339	8.1957
	EMJ	2.9170	6.8530	6.1122	191.2847	1675.6541	5.9344	8.1963
	EPF	2.7943	6.8647	6.1122	196.2588	1719.2268	5.8583	8.3277
	MoM	2.9117	6.8535	6.1122	191.4845	1677.4043	5.9314	8.2016
	MMLM	2.8745	6.8480	6.1041	192.1669	1683.3818	5.9016	8.2292
	GM	2.8441	6.8796	6.1297	195.8299	1715.4704	5.9076	8.2962
20	EML	2.5870	5.8688	5.2120	127.9766	1121.0748	4.8586	7.3232
	EMJ	2.5870	5.8681	5.2113	127.9301	1120.6680	4.8580	7.3223
	EPF	2.5010	5.8734	5.2113	131.0323	1147.8427	4.7889	7.4290
	MoM	2.5788	5.8686	5.2113	128.2107	1123.1258	4.8518	7.3320
	MMLM	2.5517	5.8743	5.2148	129.4179	1133.7009	4.8339	7.3697
	GM	2.7522	5.8776	5.2304	124.1525	1087.5759	4.9883	7.1679

Figure S1. Weibull probability distributions at different heights; (a) 20 m, (b) 40 m, (c) 60 m, (d) 80 m for year 2017-18

Table S3. Seasonal Weibull parameters and different wind speed characteristic for year 2017-18.

Season	Height (m)	k	c (m/s)	V_{avg} (m/s)	PD (W/m^2)	ED (kWh/m^2)	V_{mp} (m/s)	V_{me} (m/s)
Summer	80	3.5241	9.1933	8.2747	423.1592	934.3356	8.3626	10.4439
	60	3.4573	8.7994	7.9121	373.0807	823.7622	7.9720	10.0414
	40	3.3850	8.2203	7.3833	306.0853	675.8364	7.4125	9.4288
	20	3.2727	7.3719	6.6100	223.1726	492.7651	6.5946	8.5285

Autumn	80	3.0632	6.8505	6.1231	187.1037	408.6345	6.0213	8.0718
	60	3.2161	6.3141	5.6566	143.8413	314.1493	5.6237	7.3386
	40	3.2663	5.5660	4.9902	98.0060	214.0452	4.9767	6.4425
	20	3.1101	5.1248	4.5838	77.8666	170.0606	4.5238	6.0120
Winter	80	2.6626	7.7685	6.9051	207.7183	448.6714	6.5091	9.5878
	60	2.9249	7.0496	6.2883	148.0152	319.7129	6.1100	8.4242
	40	3.0907	6.0236	5.3862	90.2214	194.8782	5.3080	7.0790
	20	2.4927	5.0302	4.4628	58.7085	126.8103	4.0949	6.3712
Spring	80	3.8270	8.6156	7.7897	344.7895	761.2953	7.9600	9.6160
	60	3.6145	8.0886	7.2903	289.1533	638.4504	7.3954	9.1367
	40	3.2720	7.3937	6.6294	227.4187	502.1406	6.6137	8.5541
	20	2.8256	6.4714	5.7645	161.9528	357.5918	5.5445	7.8211